

Correction to: Use of fine aggregate matrix to analyze the rheological behavior of cold recycled materials

Andrea Graziani · Simone Raschia · Chiara Mignini · Alan Carter · Daniel Perraton

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A. Graziani (✉) · C. Mignini
Department ICEA of Civil and Building Engineering, and Architecture, Polytechnic University of Marche, Via Breccia Bianche, 60131 Ancona, Italy
e-mail: a.graziani@univpm.it

S. Raschia · A. Carter · D. Perraton
Construction Engineering Department, École de Technologie Supérieure (ÉTS), 1100, Notre-Dame Street West, Montréal, Canada

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